

ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ

EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Данная статья представляет собой обзор образовательных технологий, применяемых в средней общеобразовательной школе в процессе обучения иностранному языку. Авторами подчёркивается важность применения инновационных технологий в школьном образовании т.к. на сегодняшний момент они являются залогом успеха в освоении учебного предмета «Иностранный язык», а также фактором, положительно влияющим на формирование высокого уровня мотивации учащихся к изучению иностранного языка. Особое внимание уделяется необходимости активного и регулярного применения методов и инструментов инновационного характера на уроках иностранного языка для повышения общего уровня обученности.

This article is an overview of educational technologies used in secondary schools in the process of teaching a foreign language. The authors emphasize the importance of using innovative technologies in school education because at the moment they are the key to success in mastering the subject "Foreign language", as well as a factor positively influencing the formation of a high level of motivation of students to learn a foreign language. Particular attention is paid to the need for active and regular application of innovative methods and tools in foreign language lessons to improve the overall level of learning.

Ключевые слова: *новый образовательный стандарт, школьное обучение, иностранный язык, образовательные технологии, инновации, мотивация, уровень обученности.*

Key words: *new educational standard, schooling, foreign language, educational technologies, innovations, motivation, level of learning.*

The concept of modern Russian education defines a modern lesson as a multifunctional unit of the educational process, where all pedagogical influences are concentrated and implemented. Today, a modern foreign language teacher faces the task of finding optimal ways to more effectively assimilate knowledge on the subject of "Foreign Language". Due to the fact that the ed-

education system has changed significantly over the past decade, there is a need to introduce innovative technologies that could ensure the process of successful learning of a foreign language by secondary school students.

The idea of introducing innovative technologies into teaching has become widespread among teachers and methodologists all over the world. The methods of using Internet technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages are described in the works of researchers E.G. Asimov, E.N. Vishnevskaya, M.S. Balashova, O.V. Baraeva, E.S. Bachurina, L.P. Vladimirova, E.V. Voevoda, S.K. Omarova, T.A. Petrova, E.S. Polat, etc.

Thus, the introduction of a new generation of Federal State Educational Standard (FGOS) contributed to the fact that a foreign language lesson is now not complete without the use of new educational technologies [2]. Their use has allowed to create a unique informational language environment in the classroom and significantly increase motivation to learn a foreign language, which is the leading factor directing students' activities in a constructive direction. The interaction of the teacher and the student becomes possible and successful if the peculiarities of the student's motivation are considered. According to A.E. Paltov, educational technology is a set of scientifically and practically grounded methods and tools to achieve the desired result in any field of education [5, p.10].

The modern foreign language lesson is distinguished by a variety of goals and objectives, the use of information and communication technologies, electronic educational resources and is variable in the forms of conducting [4]. The choice of learning technologies necessary to achieve the main goals of language learning is a problem related to the importance of forming a set of competencies and knowledge among students. The technologies used in the framework of teaching a foreign language at school are designed to implement competence-based and personal-activity approaches.

Often, the educational process at school is based on mixed learning technologies, which implies a combination of traditional and innovative technologies. The technology of blended learning focuses on a new educational standard, on practice-oriented education, on achieving the planned learning outcomes:

- personal;
- metasubject;
- subject.

Blended learning is defined by a personality-oriented approach in which the student interacts with other students, with the teacher, as well as with the content through a thoughtful combination of Internet technologies and direct communication (innovative technologies).

The use of innovative technologies in the educational process is built around three main ideas:

- planning of learning outcomes;
- psychologization of the learning process;
- computerization of education.

The specificity of the subject "Foreign language" makes it possible to use mixed technologies. The use of these technologies in foreign language lessons increases the motivation of students, helps to overcome the psychological barrier in using a foreign language as a means of communication, makes it possible to improve the effectiveness of teaching and the quality of education. Classifying the technologies of teaching foreign languages, the following can be distinguished:

1. Technology of communicative learning. Today, in conditions of multiculturalism and dialogue of cultures, this is a basic need. It is necessary for the formation of students' communicative competence.

2. Technology of multi-level (differential) training. This technology is based on the implementation of cognitive activity of students considering their individual characteristics and capabilities, abilities, inclinations, interests. At the same time, there is encouragement in order to realize

their creative potential. One of the integral elements of this technology is a diagnostic test to identify the personal characteristics of students at school.

3. Technologies using information and communication technologies. They include Internet technologies, educational platforms, interactive whiteboards, as well as multimedia tools. The appeal to information and communication technologies is due to the fact that modern society places high demands on specialists in all fields of activity. They expand the scope of the educational process, increasing its practical orientation, contribute to the intensification of independent work of students and increase cognitive activity.

Among the technologies using ICT, two main blocks can be distinguished:

- the technology of using computer programs allows you to effectively optimize the process of learning a foreign language at all levels. Multimedia programs are designed for both classroom and independent work of students and are aimed at developing grammatical and lexical skills;

- Internet technologies help to search for information, and are also useful for the development of international scientific projects and scientific research.

4. Testing technology. Testing is a technology that enables the teacher to identify and eliminate the main "gaps" in students' knowledge.

5. Project technology is a way to carry out work on modeling social interaction, which is very important for achieving goals and solving problems with the allocation of a specific subject area. Project technologies are necessary for the formation of interdisciplinary competencies of students who develop in the process of learning a foreign language.

6. Cooperative learning is necessary for the implementation of the ideas of mutual learning. At the same time, individual and collective responsibility for success in solving certain educational tasks is carried out.

7. Game technology. A variety of games (business, situational, role-playing) are widely used. Speaking about the use of games and game elements in teaching a foreign language, it should be noted that these technologies contribute to the development of motivation to learn, language skills and speech skills. Thanks to the use of games in foreign language lessons, students develop communicative competence, which, as is known, is the main goal of teaching foreign languages.

8. Gamification technology, which methodologists recognize as the technology of the XXI century. It is believed that the term "gamification" was first used by American programmer Nick Pelling in 2002, but it has only been widely used since 2010.

In the most general sense, gamification is understood as the use of game elements and techniques used in game design in non-game contexts to achieve non-game goals [6, p. 130]. Therefore, the gamification of English language teaching can be attributed to game technology, which is conditioned by its linguistic and essential meaning.

9. The technology of critical thinking development forms diverse competencies in students, in particular, the ability to give a critical and objective assessment of the problem, the ability to systematize information (important – superfluous).

The implementation of competence-based and personal-activity approaches using these technologies provides for active and interactive forms of learning, such as business and role-playing games, analysis of specific situations, collective thinking, discussions, work on research projects, etc.

It is worth noting the so-called UNESCO technology. Its essence consists in the systematic creation, implementation and application of teaching methods, considering human and technical resources of training. The main purpose of using this technology is to form the functional language skills of students in the application of a foreign language based on integrative learning. A systematic method of planning, applying and evaluating the entire process of learning and assimilation of knowledge by considering human and technical resources and interaction between them to achieve

a more effective form of education. The concept of "UNESCO-technology" is not generally accepted in traditional pedagogy, but its principles fully correspond to the new educational model.

There are features of the introduction of innovative technologies in the educational process. The use of any teaching technology provides for the availability of a set of pedagogical tools. The tools can be units and types of educational activities, educational material, means, methods, forms of training [3]. The decisive factors are the teacher's skill, his methodological experience, approaches and logistical support. Nevertheless, today, in almost all schools, teachers use multimedia technologies to improve students' perception of educational information [1, p. 243].

In conclusion, we admit that modern technologies provide many new opportunities to make the educational process more interesting and effective. The use of new technologies has a positive impact on the quality of training, significantly expands the choice of methods and means of training, proves the effectiveness of achieving learning outcomes.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. Bordovskaya N.V. Modern educational technologies / N.V. Bordovskaya, L.A. Darinskaya, S.N. Kostromina. 2nd ed., ster. M.: KNORUS, 2011. 432 p.
2. Gabbasova L.Z. Innovative technologies in the educational process // Innovative pedagogical technologies: materials of the V International Scientific Conference (Kazan, October 2016). 2016. pp. 61-63.
3. Igna O.N. Classification of foreign language teaching technologies based on the principle of instrumentality // Bulletin of Tomsk State Pedagogical University. 2017. No 6(183). pp. 148-153. DOI 10.23951/1609-624X-2017-6-148-153. EDN YQPNAL.
4. Levchenko O.Yu. Some features of a modern foreign language lesson // Topical issues of modern philology and journalism. 2019. No.3 (34). 6 p.
5. Paltov A.E. Innovative educational technologies. Vladim. State University named after A.G. Stoletov. Vladimir: VISU Publishing House, 2018. 119 p.
6. Zarayskaya S. An easy way to quickly learn a foreign language with the help of music: 90 effective tips / S. Zarayskaya; translated by E. Tikhomirova. Moscow: Mann, Ivanov and Ferber, 2014. 193 p

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